

PURPOSEFUL FORMATION OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY EXPERIENCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: In this article, today's most important tasks of the purposeful formation of creative activity experience in the educational process of the preschool education system, the implementation of a creative approach by a specialist in the field of preschool education in his professional activity, and self-awareness measures are highlighted.

Targeted formation of creative activity experience in the educational process is one of the most important tasks today. It is difficult to believe that a specialist in the field of preschool education can implement a creative approach in his professional activity and reach the peak of self-awareness. The formation of children's experience in creative activities requires the determination of methods of organizing the educational process that will lead to the desired result. In recent decades, the ideas formed in the works of theorists of general and educational pedagogy, general and innovative pedagogy have been introduced into the educational system. theories, concepts influenced. Innovative educators also make a significant contribution to this process.

Pedagogical cooperation in the educational process can be implemented as a system of mutual relations of subjects in the following options:

a) educator - child (paints, threes, in small groups);

b) child (paints, threes, small groups of 4-7 people);

c) interaction of the general group (educator - group of children, child - group of children, small group - group of children).

These interaction options can be used with different educational technologies. For example, using educational technologies such as didactic games, all of the above options can be implemented. This will allow you to more successfully form the experience of children's creative activities during the educational process. This is confirmed by experimental data: the three academic subjects in which didactic games were used had the highest ratings.

A system of factors divided into three groups was proposed for evaluation.

1. Factors related to the educator:

- Skills;
- Pedagogical technology;
- Educator's personality, creative attitude to activities.

2. Factors related to children:

- Knowledge, skills;
- Harmony of reproductive and creative activities;
- Readiness for collective thinking activities.

3. Factors related to the relationship between educators and children. Microclimate in the group;

- personally setting up the child and the teacher for cooperation;
- the interaction of educators and children during the teaching process, cooperation.

The factors listed in terms of the importance of their influence on the formation of children's experience of creative activity are placed in the following sequence.

Educator's skills, educator's personality, his creative attitude to activities, microclimate in the group, teaching technology (organization of the pedagogical process), cooperation in the educational process, personal orientation to understanding and cooperation, children's knowledge, abilities, skills; combination

of reproductive and creative activity; readiness of children for collective thinking activity.

According to children, the factors related to the educator and his activities are the most important for the formation of their experience in creative activity, and the factors related to them are the least important. Therefore, the factors of the first group have a strong influence.

The intermediate place of influence is occupied by the factors related to the interaction between the teacher and the children. All groups have reserves to increase the importance of factors in solving this problem.

Nowadays, it is widely acknowledged that pedagogical activity has a creative nature. Creativity is an activity that creates new things based on the reorganization of existing experience and the formation of new combinations of knowledge, skills and products [1]. The result of creativity is an introduction to the innovative educational process.

There are several levels of innovation:

1. Ideas that can change pedagogical reality affirmative discovery;
2. Development and implementation of new elements of invention, pedagogical technologies;
3. Pedagogical innovation - improvements related to the adaptation and adaptation of previously used methods and tools of education and upbringing to modern conditions.

Unlike creativity in other fields (science, technology, art), the creativity of an educator does not aim to create a new, originality of social significance, because its product is always personal development. Of course, a creative educator and, moreover, an innovative educator creates his own personal pedagogical technology, but this is a tool to achieve the best result in the given conditions.

The creative potential of an educator is formed on the basis of two components, pedagogical professional and social experience.

Successful pedagogical creativity is impossible without special training and knowledge. Only an educated and specially trained educator is able to find new original methods and solutions based on the understanding of the essence of the problem through a deep analysis of the situations, creative imagination and thought experience.

An educator often has to solve many typical and non-standard pedagogical tasks in changing conditions. In solving these problems, the educator, like any researcher, builds his activity according to the general rules of heuristic search: analyzes the pedagogical situation; compiles the result according to the initial data; checks the assumptions and analyzes the funds needed to achieve the desired result; evaluates the received information; creates new problems.

Therefore, the creative pedagogical activity consists of the following stages: the search for a hypothesis, plan and way to implement an idea, the emergence of a concept, its development and transformation into an idea. The experience of creativity is acquired by the educator on the condition of systematic exercises in solving specially selected tasks that reflect the pedagogical reality and organizing both educational and career-oriented activities of future educators.

Often, the field of expression of the educator's creativity narrows unintentionally, returning it to a non-standard, original solution to pedagogical problems. At the same time, the educator's creativity is also manifested in solving communicative tasks, and serves as a unique basis and basis of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical creativity in the field of personality is manifested as creative individuality based on the self-awareness of the educator, defining individual methods of their professional growth and building a self-improvement program. Levels of pedagogical creativity. The following levels of pedagogical creativity are distinguished:

1. Repetition of prepared recommendations (elementary interaction with the group): the educator uses interaction. Adjusts his influence according to results, but he works

"according to the manual", "according to the pattern" according to the experience of other educators.

2. When creativity is manifested in a skillful choice and a suitable combination of educational content, methods and forms already known to the educator, starting from its planning, optimizing the activity in the lesson.

3. Using the creative possibilities of live communication with children.

4. Using ready-made methods with the introduction of a personal beginning that corresponds to the creative personality of the educator, the personal characteristics of the child, the specific level of development of the group.

Often, creativity is associated only with advanced pedagogical experience.

However, this is not entirely true. Under best practices should be understood the high skill of the educator. There may not be anything new or original in his experience, but he can serve as an example for educators who have not yet mastered pedagogical skills. In this sense, the achievements of a master teacher are virtues that deserve to be spread. This is characteristic of the first and second levels of pedagogical creativity. The third and fourth levels of pedagogical creativity include elements of creative research, innovation, originality and usually lead to innovation. This opens up new ways in educational practice and pedagogical science. The result of this may be a partial change in the structure of education and pedagogical technologies, as well as global changes in the field of education. Therefore, it is an innovative experience that needs to be analyzed, summarized and disseminated first. Signs of a creative person. The creative potential of any person, including an educator, is characterized by a number of personal characteristics, which are called signs of a creative personality. There are various lists of such features. Some authors emphasize a person's ability to perceive and formulate alternatives, doubt at first sight and avoid superficial formula; the ability to solve a problem and at the same time to move away from reality, to see the future; the ability to refuse to refer to the authorities; the ability to see a familiar object from a completely new point of view,

in a new context; willingness to move away from the usual balance of life, to abandon theoretical judgments, divided into black and white, for uncertainty and search.

A more widespread functional approach, according to which professional pedagogical activity is a certain system of interrelated and pedagogically appropriate actions that form skills. It is worth noting that the quality of the formation of these skills is used as a criterion for the success of the educator's work: the higher the quality of the skills, the more successfully the educator solves pedagogical problems, the higher the quality of the educational process. An unprofessional behavior of an educator naturally lowers its quality.

N.V. Kuzmina, who developed the structure of the educator's activity, identified five functional components: 1) gnostic; 2) design; 3) constructive; 4) organizational and 5) communicative.

1. Gnostic component (Greek gnosis - knowledge) refers to the educator's knowledge. This is not only knowing your subject, but also knowing the methods of pedagogical communication, the psychological characteristics of children, as well as their own about self-knowledge (self and activity).
2. The design component includes ideas about the prospective tasks of education and training, as well as strategies and methods for achieving them includes.
3. The constructive component is the personal activity of the educator and the design features of the child's activity, taking into account teaching and the direct goals of education (lesson, lesson, group cycle).
4. The communicative component is the characteristics of the educator's communicative activity, the specific characteristics of his interaction with children. Attention is paid to the connection with the effectiveness of pedagogical activities aimed at achieving didactic (educational - educational) goals.
5. The organizational part is a system of abilities of educators to organize their activities, as well as the active work of children. It should be noted that all the

components of this model are often described through the skill system of educators. Methodical knowledge allows them to answer the question of how to do this, but they now think that the exercise will be done by children, not for them. It is the knowledge of how to teach others.

The first (preparatory) stage is aimed at creating conditions to ensure the quality of the general and individual lessons. It includes:

- development of the educational process schedule for the year;
- development of a thematic plan for each academic term;
- development of abstract plans for each lesson;
- selection of specific means and methods of physical education, forms of organization of the educational process (basic, leading and special exercises; number of repetitions of each exercise; duration of individual exercises; general pedagogical methods - verbal teaching of motor movements, increase visual and specific methods and physical qualities).

The educator's professionogram was developed in 1967 by E.V. Kuzmina. The requirements for the educator's personality include the necessary social and professional qualities: high civic responsibility, social activity, love for children, true intelligence, spiritual culture, high professionalism, innovative style of scientific and pedagogic thinking, the ability to make creative decisions, constant determined by the need for self-discipline, physical and mental health, professional work harmony. A characteristic feature of an educator's personality is reliability (a sense of duty, responsibility, intolerance of shortcomings and moral defects, etc.), personal orientation (interest in the profession, pedagogical intention and inclination), with the manifestation of such important qualities as pedagogical tactics. depends. An intuitive sense of proportionality, pedagogical justice - the objectivity of the educator, the level of his moral education, the reputation of the educator.

Three interrelated components of the educator's activity: constructive (selecting, planning and building educational material); organizational (management);

communicative (establishing pedagogically appropriate relations of the teacher with children, educators, parents).

Therefore, pedagogical creativity is a process that begins with the assimilation of what has already been collected (adaptation, repetition, increase of knowledge and experience), replacing the existing experience. This is the path from adaptation to the pedagogical situation to its change, this is the essence of the dynamics of the educator's creativity.

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